

DETERMINATION OF THE PROCESS WINDOW FOR ULTRASONIC WELDING OF CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

B.J. Weteringe, H.E.N. Bersee and A.Beukers

*Disciplinary Group for Composite Materials & Structures
Faculty of Aerospace Engineering
Delft University of Technology,
Kluyverweg 1, 2629 HS Delft, The Netherlands*

ABSTRACT

During the last decade new composites have been developed, based on thermoplastic matrices. Compared with metals, these composites offer significant weight reduction at no cost penalty, preservation of environment, preservation of natural resources/energy and improvement of the work environment. Compared with thermoset composites these materials also offer a reduction of manufacturing cost.

The high mechanical requirements of structural aircraft components necessitates the usage of continuous fibers in composites. Currently available continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics are APC-2TM and CetexTM. CetexTM is available as laminates (Aramid, glass or carbon fibre reinforced PEI or PPS) with a consumer dependant build-up. The laminates are semi-manufactured articles and can be formed into a desired product shape by means of a thermoforming process (rubber forming, diaphragm forming).

As continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics become more important for use in primary aircraft structures like rudders and ailerons, there is a need for developing processes in order to produce such structures. One of the main topics involves welding of thermoplastic composites. Since thermoplastics have the ability to melt and solidify, this property can be used to bond two components to each other (for instance welding of ribs, stiffeners and spars to the skin). This production method reduces assembly time and structural weight compared with conventional assembly technologies.

One of the welding processes for thermoplastics is ultrasonic welding (well-known in the food industry). Main advantage of ultrasonic welding compared with other welding methods (resistance welding, induction welding) is that there is no foreign material included in the weld. This results in a higher weld strength and eliminates problems with different thermal expansion of the materials.

The objective of this paper is to provide the process window for ultrasonic welding of carbon reinforced PEI. A large number of specimens were produced with different process parameters. Mechanical tests (lap-shear) and microscopy were used to evaluate the weld quality.

KEY TERMS: welding, energy director, lap-shear, carbon, PEI

INTRODUCTION

The increasing interest in continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics necessitates the development of processing techniques. One of the main advantages of welding thermoplastics is that the labour cost can be decreased significantly. Also, the composite material does not have to be weakened by holes for rivets and bolts. As a result designs of structures can be optimized, resulting in weight reduction.

Many different welding technologies for joining continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastics have been developed during the last ten years [1,2]. Three of these have been proven to be the most suitable: resistance welding, induction welding and ultrasonic welding [3]. Ultrasonic welding results in the highest possible weld strengths. The bond strength is almost equal to that achieved by compression molding [4]. Previous work on ultrasonic welding involves the development of the welding technique [5-7] and especially the characterization of the use of energy directors [5-7,9,10]. However, a defined process window for the ultrasonic welding of continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastics has not been developed yet.

The purpose of this paper is to provide the process window for the ultrasonic welding of glass and carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics. Both the welding equipment and the shape of the energy director are fixed. The most important variables are pressure and weld time. Lap-shear tests and microscopic evaluation were used to develop the process window for the different materials.

EQUIPMENT & MATERIALS

The machine used for the welding of the specimen is the Branson, type 8200. The frequency is 20kHz, the pressure ranges from 10 – 100 psi and the weld time ranges from 0.1 – 4.0 seconds. Also the trigger pressure, down speed and hold time can be set. However, the latter three are kept constant during this research. The

amplitude of vibration can not be changed, since the machine does not contain this option. Research on this subject has been done by A.Benatar and Z.Cheng [5,8].

Figure 1 shows the horn and bottom plate, which were chosen according to ASTM standard D1002 for the determination of the lap-shear strength.

First of all laminates had to be consolidated out of prepreg material. The material is continuous carbon fibre reinforced PEI (Ultem), since the shear strength can then be compared with the shear strength of resistance welded specimen. The laminate build-up is 8 plies 0/90.

A hydraulic flat platen press was used to heat the prepreg layers up to 320°C at a pressure of 2 bar. Pressure was then increased to 10 bar and after 10 minutes the press was cooled down at a pressure of 10 bar.

When a laminate with less plies is welded, it often happens that the laminate is the first to fail during the lap-shear test. For this reason the lap-joint width is chosen to be 12.7 mm instead of 25.4 mm. The lap-shear specimens were tested with a 20 kN Zwick tensile testing machine at a speed of 1.3 mm/min. The dimensions of the energy director are based on figure 2 [9,10]. Since $W = 12.7$ mm, the height of the triangle should be 1.6 mm and the width 3.2 mm. However, better results were obtained when the triangle height was 2 mm and the width 4 mm. Therefore, a die was developed with two triangular shapes based on these dimensions (see figure 3).

Figure 1: Test set-up for specimen welding

Figure 2: dimensions of the energy director

Figure 3: Aluminum die for the consolidation of the energy directors

A flat hot platen press was used to melt the triangular energy director onto the laminate. An exact volume granules of PEI (Ultem 1010) were dried in an oven and placed in the triangles. The carbon/PEI laminate was placed on top and an aluminum casing was used to fixate the laminate. The pressure was 2 bar and the temperature 315°C. The result is a laminate with two strips of energy director, which can be cut into two halves, both containing an energy director. With a diamond saw the laminates were cut into strips of 12.7 mm width.

EXPERIMENTS

From preliminary welding trials it appeared that there was a lot of scatter in the test results of the lap-shear test. The scatter could be the result of small misalignments in the test set-up. The influence of this misalignment was also tested. Therefore, continuous carbon fibre reinforced PPS specimens were welded. 1 batch of 10 specimens was welded with a misalignment of the energy director of 1.5 mm, while the other batch of 10 specimens was welded with the energy director exactly in the centerline of the horn (see figure 4). The weld parameters time and pressure were 3,5 sec. and 10 psi respectively, based on preliminary parameter investigation. The trigger pressure, down speed and hold time were kept constant. Also, two batches of continuous carbon fibre reinforced PEI were welded to verify if there is a difference in welding results of semi-crystalline and amorphous matrices. The weld parameters time and pressure were again chosen according to preliminary testing and were 4 sec. and 20 psi respectively. Again, the trigger pressure, down speed and hold time were not changed.

Figure 4: Position of the energy director on the carbon/PEI specimen

The test conditions and batch numbers, as used for the determination of the process window for ultrasonic welding of continuous fiber reinforced PEI, are illustrated in table 1. Each batch S# consists of 10 specimens. The weld time is limited by the machine (max. 4 sec) and the pressure is limited to about 70 psi because the fibers will be damaged when higher forces are used.

Table 1: Test matrix for welding of carbon/PEI

Pressure [Psi]	10	30	50	70
Weld time [s]				
2	S1	S4	S7	
3	S2	S5	S8	
4	S3	S6	S9	S10

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Misalignments of the energy director only lead to a lower mean value of the strength. The mean shear strength for the specimens with the energy director 1.5 mm from the center of the horn was 15.4 N/mm², where the mean shear strength for the specimens with the energy director exactly in the center of the horn was 23.0 N/mm². The standard deviation within the two batches however, was still remarkable high. This might be caused by the process parameters used.

Table 2 gives an overview of the welded batches S#, including test results. Calculations showed that all the test results fit into a Weibull distribution. The standard deviation given in the table, is based on this distribution.

Table 2: Overview of the welded carbon/PEI batches, including lap-shear results.

Batch no.	Weld pressure (psi)	Weld Time (sec)	Weld strength (N/mm ²)	Std. Dev. (N/mm ²)
S1	10	2	23.0	3.32
S2	10	3	24.1	3.35
S3	10	4	24.6	2.13
S4	30	2	25.0	3.19
S5	30	3	28.3	1.51
S6	30	4	27.8	4.78
S7	50	2	25.9	3.65
S8	50	3	31.5	2.57
S9	50	4	28.2	1.86
S10	70	4	27.9	1.11

Figures 5 and 6 show the weld strength as a function of the weld time and weld pressure respectively.

Figure 5: Weld strength as a function of the weld time at different pressures.

When a weld pressure of 10 psi is used, increasing the weld time has a positive effect on the weld strength. However, at a pressure of 30 psi this effect is eliminated. And at even a higher pressure (50 psi) the weld strength decreases at longer weld times.

Figure 6: Weld strength as a function of the weld pressure at different weld times.

When a short weld time of 2 seconds is used, increasing the pressure has a positive effect on the weld strength. It appears that the effect of the pressure is most when a weld time of 3 seconds is used. At 4 seconds, increasing the pressure does not make any difference. The weld strength remains about the same. Since batch S9, welded with 3 seconds and 50 psi, had a low standard deviation compared to the other batches and the weld strength was high, an extra batch was welded at 70 psi to verify if a pressure increase would result in higher weld strength. As expected, the fibers were damaged at this pressure. The weld strength was about the same as at 50 psi.

Figure 7 shows the data set range for each batch. Not only the obtained weld strength for each batch is of importance to determine the process window, but also the data range for each batch is considered to be of influence on the optimum process window for welding of continuous fiber reinforced PEI, because the scatter in the test results within a batch is dependant on the process parameters. Some combinations of parameters might be on the boundary of the process window, which could result in incomplete welding of the specimens.

Figure 7: Data set range for batch 1-10

Batches S1, S4 and S7 were welded with a weld time of 2 seconds. There is no concentration of data points within these batches, which means that this weld time does not guarantee reproducible welds. For batch S2, welded at a low pressure of 10 psi, the same appears, though there seems to be a shift of the datapoints to the right side of the range. Batch S3, welded at 10 psi of pressure during 4 seconds, already shows some improvements compared with S1 and S2. The data range is much smaller and there are no outliers to the left side of the range. However, the mean weld strength for this batch is still at the low side. Batch S6 really shows a lot of scatter in the test results. The data range is almost overlapping the whole range of all batches. However, it is remarkable that the highest weld strength of all specimens is within this batch. Batches S5, S8, S9 and S10 all show a high weld strength and a rather small data range.

Microscopic photos were made of samples of batches S2, S5, S8 and S9 to evaluate the quality of the bond. It appeared that the welded area is not even recognizable in some specimens of batches S5, S8 and S9, which means that the consolidation of the two laminates was optimal. What is of great interest is that there are no voids inside the weld area. In figure 8, photos of the bond line of specimens of batches S2 and S8 are shown. For the specimen from S2 it is visible that the bond was not complete. The bond line of the specimen of S8 is clearly visible. Also, a general view of the bond line of the specimens which have the highest weld strength and little scatter, is shown.

Figure 8: Microscopic views of a specimen of S2 (left); S8 (middle); and a general view of the bond line for batches S5, S8 and S9 (right).

CONCLUSIONS

Ultrasonic welding is a promising joining method for continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics. The optimum weld time for continuous fiber reinforced PEI is around 3 seconds. The optimum weld pressure lies in the range from 30 psi to the pressure where fiber damage occurs (≈ 60 psi). The bond line does not contain voids and is perfectly consolidated. Weld strengths are very high and there is no exotic material in the weld, which is the case in other welding methods like induction and resistance welding. A disadvantage of the process is the scatter in the weld strength, which might be caused by the short process time. By choosing the correct process parameters this scatter can be reduced. In table 3 the combinations of pressure and time, which resulted in the most reproducible high weld strengths are marked.

Table 3: Process window

Pressure [Psi]	10	30	50	70
2	S1	S4	S7	
3	S2	S5	S8	
4	S3	S6	S9	S10

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